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IDENTIFY OPPORTUNITIES AND THREATS TOURISM DESTINATIONS PANCURAN 13 AND "SERWITI" GUCI CURUG TEGAL, JAWA TENGAH

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Abstract

This community service activity aims to identify opportunities and challenges for the Curuk Serwiti tourist park in Guci Tegal, Central Java. The tourist destination Pancuran 13 and Curug "Serwiti" is managed by BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTO GUCI". The service methods carried out are training, discussions and interviews related to the development of tourism potential which is managed by BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTO GUCI". The focus of activities is directed at identifying opportunities and threats in developing these two tourist destinations. This is because, in the surrounding environment, other tourist destinations have mushroomed which are managed by private parties and also compete with local destinations outside Tegal which also offer natural tourism. The results of this community service activity have been carried out well with indicators: (1) the number of participants and SMEs involved was 100%, (2) increased knowledge and insight related to BUMDES management, especially in managing tourist destinations, (3) gained knowledge related to motivation endeavor, (4) publication in scientific journals with the theme of identifying opportunities and threats as well as policy recommendations. It is important to note that the development of digital services and the closing of the digital divide in social media are essential for the development of tourism in the region.

JEL classification: M38, O33

Keywords: training, tourism potential, analysis of opportunities and threats, policy recommendations, social media, digital divide

1. Introduction

Guci Village is famous for having a lot of abundant natural resource potential. This can of course be used to increase community empowerment and explore hidden local tourism potential. Likewise, it can also optimize tourist destinations that already exist so that they can be more developed and advanced. One of the famous resources in Guci village is the hot springs from Mount Slamet. This spring can be used as a tourist commodity where its presence can also be a trigger to increase other tourism potential.

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Some of the potential developed by the Guci village government/ BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTO GUCI" is TWA (Natural Tourism Park) Pancuran 13 Guci commonly called Pancuran 13 is one of the many hot springs around Guci, Tegal. Next is also the "Serwiti Waterfall Tour" which is known as "Secret Paradise".

The history of Pancuran 13 Guci begins with a cave that has 13 hot springs, then under the cave, the local people made a shower with as many springs as the water that comes out so it is called Pancuran 13. This bath in Guci is believed to have the property of being able to cure skin diseases, scientifically speaking. This could happen because the hot water contains sulfur (<https://www.nativeindonesia.com/pancuran-13-guci/>, accessed 28 December 2023). Meanwhile, Serwiti Waterfall, which previously was not managed optimally, is now starting to improve for the better. This new tourist attraction is managed by BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI" Guci Village, Bumijawa District, Tegal Regency. Chairman of BUMDES and manager of Serwiti Waterfall, Budi Kuswanto, said that the name Serwiti was taken from the name of a bird. This is because in the past there were so many Serwiti birds that it was finally given the name "SERWITI Waterfall Tourism". The location of this waterfall is exactly above the 13 Guci fountain. It turns out that the beauty of Curug Serwiti is also slowly becoming known besides Guci tourism which is already known nationally (<https://kumparan.com/panturapost/curug-serwiti-wisata-baru-di-desa-guci-kabupaten-tegal-1vnNjUoW3i/full>, access 14 December 2023).

To improve the economy through the potential that exists in the Guci Village environment, Bumijawa District, the Guci Village Government needs to develop the potential that exists in the existence of Pancuran 13 and Curug Serwiti, including managing other businesses that can be explored and developed in the future. Therefore, this paper aims to identify opportunities and challenges as well as policy recommendations for the existence of Pancuran 13 and Serwiti Waterfall tourism in Guci Tegal, Central Java.

2. A Glance at BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTO GUCI"

Law Number 6 of 2014 which regulates Villages Chapter The hope is that a village can increase the income of the community and the village government. Likewise, Regulation No. 4 of 2015 explains the establishment, administration management, and dissolution of BUMDES.

Village-Owned Enterprise (BUMDES) "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI" Guci Village was formed based on Guci Village Regulation Number 06 of 2021 concerning BUMDES. In the administration and management of BUMDES, several elements must be fulfilled, including; Advisors held by the local Village Head, Management Body, Supervisory Body and Implementing Body. The management of BUMDES was determined and confirmed by the Guci Village Government on December 1, 2021. Furthermore, all elements will carry out their duties and functions starting from January 1, 2021.

VISION AND MISSION OF BUMDES BERKAH TIRTO GUCI

Vision: Realizing the welfare of the Guci Village Community through the development of economic businesses and social services with the motto GOTONG ROYONG

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1. Improving the Village Economy
2. Increasing community efforts in managing village economic potential
3. Increase the village's original income
4. Improve the community's economy
5. Creating a Creative Economy in Order to Eradicate Poverty

BUMDES MANAGEMENT

The structure of the BUMDES Implementing Body "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI" is:

1. Village Head as advisor: H SOLEH
2. Director of Bumdes: Imamudin
3. Bumdes Secretary: Amin Maijun
4. Bumdes Treasurer: Akhmad Syauqi
5. Tourism Division: Ali Burhan

One of the activities that has been implemented is the management of Pancuran 13 and Curug Serwiti tourism. Apart from that, in the future, there is also a desire to be able to manage homestays, produce processed food typical of local communities, and increase craft businesses and other businesses that are still being identified and developed to increase the income of local communities.

The existence of BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTA GUCCI" is expected to support the income of Guci Village because when BUMDES can manage various businesses it can have an impact on the activities and performance of village communities. It is hoped that villages can become independent and resilient in facing future challenges. When empowerment through the creative industry impacts a tourism destination, in general, the minimum needs of the community have been met, so it is hoped that the community will be healthier and happier and their work enthusiasm will increase. The aim is to create an independent and competitive village (Damiasih, 2021; Pangestu, 2008; Witariadi et al., 2023; Sardinia & Purnawan, 2015).

3. Problem

The Pancuran 13 Tour and the Serwiti Waterfall Tour are tours developed by BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI" and are located in the Guci tourist area in Tegal, Central Java. This tour provides very interesting natural views, besides the air there is very cool to enjoy. Travel Pancuran 13 from word of mouth is known to be able to be used to treat skin diseases. Meanwhile, Serwiti waterfall is known as "Secret Paradise" because it is very beautiful. Photo spot locations for selfies and family photos are provided in a very attractive way, with waterfalls and rivers and beautiful natural beauty with clean air.

However, the problems faced are the proliferation of new tourist destinations managed by private parties which tend to be managed professionally and located nearby, in addition to other areas outside Guci which offer the same advantages. Their existence is an alternative for local

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and foreign tourists to visit and enjoy because they tend to be offered more attractive tour packages. Private destinations also have a much higher digital presence and social media activity.

4. Implementation and Methods of Community Service

This community service uses several methods. The method used was training held at the "Guci Kencana Jaya" hotel located in Guci Tegal, Central Java. The activity was attended by several UKMs consisting of processed food UKMs, delivery of mental and circumcision services, craft UKMs and representatives of the BUMDES management "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI". This activity also included the involvement of students from the Management Science Study Program, Doctoral Program and Digital Business Study Program at, the Faculty of Business and Economics, Islamic University of Indonesia. Apart from that, it also involved students and lecturers from Széchenyi István University of Győr, Hungary. Results of Collaboration between the Islamic University of Indonesia and ODDEA involving Universities from Central-Eastern Europe.

Apart from business management training, the team also held interactive discussions and interviews with tourism actors and several representatives from BUMDES. The team places greater emphasis and focus on developing Pancuran 13 tourism and Serwiti waterfall tourism and diversifying other businesses that can support each other. Therefore, the output that will result from this activity is; the identification of opportunities and challenges for the Pancuran 13 and Serwiti waterfall tourist destinations and recommendations for future policies that can be implemented by tourism actors and interested stakeholders to achieve the Vision and Mission of BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI".

5. Implementation of Service

Figure 1. Training activities for UKM and BUMDES Representatives "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI".

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The implementation of community service is:

1. Conduct training related to SME Business Management and BUMDES Governance "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI". The training participants were SMEs and several representatives of BUMDES managers. Likewise, it also involves students from the Management Science Study Program, Doctoral Program and Digital Business Study Program, Faculty of Business and Economics, Islamic University of Indonesia. Apart from that, it also involved experts from the University of Montenegro. Results of collaboration between the Islamic University of Indonesia and ERASMUS ODDEA involving universities from Europe.

2. Conduct discussions with local SMEs and several representatives from BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI".

The team held discussions about managing SME businesses so that they can be successful, starting from identifying the problems faced, providing business development consultations and providing solutions that can be followed up in the short and long term.

3. Conduct interviews with several representatives present from BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI". for the management and development of the Pancuran 13 and Curug SERWITI tourist destinations.

4. Next, the team conducted interviews with other tourism actors

5. The team conducted an identification and mapping survey of tourism potential in Guci and its surroundings

6. The team identified opportunities and threats to tourist destinations managed by BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI"

5. Results and discussions

After carrying out the activities, the team identified and mapped opportunities and threats to the Pancuaran 13 and Curug Serwiti tourist destinations. The results are as follows:

Opportunity:

1. Attraction of Tourist Attractions; It has the attraction of being a natural tourist attraction that offers genuine hot springs pristine natural views and attractive waterfalls.

2. Accessibility: tourist destination locations have easy access and are not too difficult to reach.

3. Local wisdom: offering local wisdom while maintaining the traditions and habits of local communities by selling original fruit and vegetables directly picked from trees and plants at very affordable prices

4. Ticket Prices: the ticket prices offered are relatively cheap and affordable for local, let alone foreign, tourists

5. Carrying Capacity: Facilities and infrastructure are relatively well provided although they still need to be improved

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6. Accommodation: accommodation in the form of hotels, homestays and similar motels at affordable prices

Threat

1. Similar tourist destinations: Similar tourism that offers natural tourist attractions and views from other areas creates a threat for local and foreign tourists to switch and are no longer interested in visiting again

2. Optimal service from similar destinations outside Guci: excellent and optimal service from similar tourism actors

3. Strong competitor social networks: strong and compact competitor tourism social networks make coordination with tourism actors better

4. Expertise of competing tourism actors: increasing the expertise and education of competing tourism actors must be followed up in a balanced manner

5. Incessant promotion of competitors' social media: promotion of competitors' social media has become a strategic issue to be paid attention to by tourism actors in Guci and its surroundings

6. Governance of established competitors: BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI" must continue to improve to be better

6. Conclusions and recommendations

The service was carried out smoothly and well. Sustainability and intensity in the future can be continued with other activities used to support the success of tourism development managed by BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI". There is a need for strategies and policies that are related to each other and can be carried out in a holistic and integrated manner involving the role of government, universities, community leaders, NGOs, SMEs and other tourism actors. The strategies and policies offered can be in terms of marketing strategy, operations/production, human resources, finance and organizational governance. It is particularly important to overcome the digital divide, as this is an area where there is a significant gap with private competitors, for example increasing social media activity could be a breakthrough for the destination.

Acknowledgements

The Service Team would like to thank all parties, especially SMEs in the Guci tourist location and its surroundings and BUMDES "BERKAH TIRTA GUCI", Adrienn Veisz, and Barbara Huszár from Széchenyi István University of Győr, Hungary, who has helped with this service activity.

Co-funded by the European Union. This outcome was prepared in the framework of the project Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia "ODDEA" Project No. 101086381 Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1. Views and opinions expressed are however

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In particular, special thanks are expressed to the DPPM of the Management Department, Faculty of Business and Economics, Indonesian Islamic University, Yogyakarta for the co-funding support, both material and non-material, for this service activity with Contract No. 009/Hibrah PKM/Jur.Mnj/01/XI/2023. Likewise, thank you for the support from students of the Management Science Study Program, Doctoral Program, Faculty of Business and Economics, Islamic University of Indonesia.

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